

Effect of Multiple Taxation on the Financial Performance of SMEs in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Despite the significant contribution of SMEs to the Nigerian economy, challenges still persist that hinder the growth and development of the sector. One of the challenges, which is the focal point of the current research work, is multiple taxation. The research is a quantitative analysis that relies on questionnaires to elicit responses from respondents for analysis purposes. The population of is 6,131 SMEs operators in Oyo state. A sample size of 357 participants, selected in Ibadan, was drawn from the population using Taro Yamane of which 218 copies of questionnaire was duly completed and returned. Hypotheses were tested using correlation analysis. The findings from the survey revealed that multiple taxation greatly influences performance of SMEs in Ibadan, Oyo State. It was therefore recommended that government should repeal tax laws inimical to survival and growth of SMEs and unify all tax frameworks in order to dissuade tax duplication by state organs and its cronies. Additionally, the activities of phony tax officials and touts who collect fees, levies, and taxes should be checked by the government.

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Introduction

In recent times the world economy has developed tremendously, and this has been linked with activities of Small and Medium Scale Enterprises (SMEs), especially in developing countries. The SME sector is the backbone of major developed economies, as well as important contributors to employment, economic and export growth. In Nigeria, SMEs account for 96% of the total number of businesses in the country and contribute about 50% to the national GDP (PwC, 2020). According to a survey conducted in 2018 In Nigeria, over 41.5 million MSME businesses operate in the country (NBS & SMEDAN, 2018). Multiple taxes and levies continue to be a burden on tax-paying businesses in Nigeria, particularly micro, small, and medium-sized enterprises (MSMEs). Additionally, there is a lack of coordination between the federal and state tax agencies. In addition to the Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS) and local governments, Nigeria has 36 state tax authorities. Each of these entities has the constitutional authority to increase taxes, which has resulted in an increased tax burden and business complaints. Nigeria was ranked 159th out of 190 economies on PwC's 2020 index of ease of paying taxes (PwC, 2020).

The significant contributions of the SMEs to economic development and growth of a country notwithstanding, a good number of these businesses elapse before their 5th anniversary. Various

cause factors exist to explain the trend, but multiple taxation has become one of the most significant contributory factors to the demise of these businesses after the 5th year. Many governments policy's view and treat small and medium-sized businesses in the same way as large corporations. Their size and nature, however, set them apart. As a result, when dealing with small and medium-sized businesses, these unique characteristics must be considered. When levying taxes on these enterprises, it is critical to consider how these tax policies can be designed to promote the growth of SMEs and how they can be administered most effectively. The significance of SMEs as engines of economic growth and development is frequently overlooked.

Taxation can contribute to development and welfare in three ways: it must generate sufficient funds to finance high-quality public services and social transfers, it must provide incentives for increased employment and the efficient and sustainable use of natural resources, and it must be able to reallocate income. However, in the case of SMEs, taxation must take their income and survival needs into account. It is prudent to allow them sufficient profit to expand their businesses. Tax policies must be designed in such a way that they do not encourage SMEs to remain in the informal sector or to evade or avoid paying taxes. Additionally, many small businesses in Africa, including Nigeria, prefer to remain in the informal sector because perceived benefits outweigh perceived costs. Businesses rarely see their tax contributions in action, and compliance costs are prohibitively high, discouraging compliance. Additionally, the government is discouraged from collecting taxes from small businesses, as the cost of monitoring and collecting taxes from small businesses by revenue authorities, whose resources are typically limited, frequently outweighs the revenues generated by small businesses (Ocheni & Gemade, 2015).

Despite the significant contribution of SMEs to the Nigerian economy, challenges still persist that hinder the growth and development of the sector. One of the challenges, which is the focal point of the current research work is Multiple taxation. Ranked as the 5th most pressing problem currently facing business in Nigeria; It was observed that multiple taxation continues to remain a huge cause for concern to SMEs amidst outdated tax laws. Many businesses believe that the government needs to do more in streamlining taxes across the different tiers of government (PwC, 2020). Nigeria, with the possible exception of the United States, has probably the most tax authorities in the world. Nonetheless, in comparison to Nigeria's tax administration system, the United States maintains a far more robust database of taxpayers and payments. Additionally, the United States' tax-to-GDP ratio is 26%, more than four times that of Nigeria. Multiple taxes and levies, a lack of coordination between federal and state agencies, and the absence of a central technology platform for the ease of tax payment are just some of the challenges faced by MSMEs.

The study's overall objective is to determine the effect of multiple taxation on the financial performance of SMEs in Ibadan, Oyo State. The specific objectives are to:

1. Examine the link between multiple taxation and the survival of small businesses.
2. Determine whether the size and capacity of small businesses to pay taxes has an effect on their survival.

Hypotheses

To adequately address the study's problems, the following research hypotheses were developed. These hypotheses were stated as follows in Null form:

H0₁: There is no significant relationship between multiple taxation and SMEs' Performance.

H0₂: The relationship between SMEs' size and its ability to pay taxes does not significantly affect their Performance.

Literature Review

SMEs

The concept of a small and medium-sized enterprise is relative and dynamic. Uncertainty, innovation, and evolution are all characteristics of SMEs. A thorough understanding of SMEs requires an in-depth knowledge of their characteristics. In Nigeria, SMEs are typically small in size, lack a robust organizational structure, and lack a strong management culture. While urban SMEs are more structured, rural SMEs are less structured. This is a critical characteristic of SMEs in Nigeria. SMEs are typically one-person operations or partnerships, though they may be registered as limited liability companies (Ocheni & Gemade, 2015). This ownership style has resulted in small and medium-sized enterprises having a simpler management structure and being easier to manage than large firms, as well as having fewer employees and, in some cases, a low level of education among some SMEs' owners.

The term "Small and medium-sized enterprises" varies according to context, author, and country in which these businesses operate. In the United Kingdom, for example, SMEs are defined as businesses with annual revenue of less than £2 million and fewer than 200 paid employees. In Japan, SMEs are defined as businesses with a minimum paid-up capital of 100 million yen and fewer than 300 employees. In Nigeria, small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) are defined as those with fewer than 100 employees for small businesses and up to 500 or more for medium-sized enterprises (CBN report, various issues). In Nigeria, SMEs are broadly defined as businesses with annual revenue of less than N100 million and/or fewer than 300 employees, with a capital investment of less than N2 million (excluding land costs) or a minimum of N5 million naira (CBN reports) (Ilemona, Nwite & Oyedokun, 2019).

SMEs are almost identical to sole proprietorships in that there is no legal personality between them and their owners, which means that the lifespan of SMEs is determined by the owners' lives; when the owner dies, the business also dies. Another distinguishing feature of the SMEs sector in some countries is its heterogeneity, ranging from small retail establishments to highly compensated professionals and highly manufactured organizations. Small and medium-sized businesses are also likely to take on a variety of organizational forms, including sole proprietorships (one-person operations), large corporations (public or private), professionals, and partnerships (Ocheni & Gemade, 2015).

Additionally, because of their small capital, SMEs' manufacturing processes are labor intensive and manual, and they are always suppliers to large manufacturing firms, as their products are primarily raw materials. Similarly, to a sole proprietorship, SMEs require less startup capital than large corporations. Additionally, the contribution of SMEs to tax revenue is typically less than their contributions to output and employment, even though SMEs have not become competitive enough to increase their share of output, despite the fact that they account for three-

fifths of the number of manufacturing industries that rely entirely on SMEs for supplies (products) (Ocheni & Gemade, 2015).

Multiple Taxation

While taxation is not the most important source of revenue for the government in terms of revenue generated, it is the most important source of revenue for the government in terms of certainty and consistency of taxation. In a socially oriented economy, taxation can generate only a small portion of revenue, whereas in a capitalist economy, taxation can generate a greater portion of government revenue. Taxation has been a source of contention for both the government and the taxpayer since the dawn of civilization. Taxation has long been a source of contention and several political conflicts. Numerous economic theories have been proposed to run an effective system, based on their importance. Taxation is a compulsory levy by the government on its subjects' income, capital, or consumption through its various agencies (Ocheni & Gemade, 2015).

It is observed that widespread harassment of SMEs and corruption by some government employees, many governments regulatory agencies, and multiple taxes and levies imposed by various levels of government result in a high cost of doing business for SMEs, and thus entrepreneurs frequently lose motivation. This is due to the absence of a harmonized and gazetted tax regime that would enable manufacturers to incorporate recognized and approved tax levies. The Nigerian Federation is divided into three tiers of government: the federal government, 36 state governments, and the Federal Capital Territory, as well as 774 local governments. The precise number of taxes levied on businesses appears to vary significantly across Nigeria's various states and local governments, and businesses may be subject to as many as 30 different taxes, charges, fees, and levies per year - and in some instances, taxed on the event or asset itself - levied by the three tiers of government. As a result, issues such as poor financial planning and management arise (Tabet & Onyeukwu, 2019).

Taxation is fundamentally composed of three types of structures: proportional, progressive, and regressive. Proportional taxation is defined as a type of taxation in which the taxpayer is assessed an amount proportional to his earnings, progressive taxation levies a higher rate on higher income earners, and regressive taxation levies a higher rate on lower income earners (Onyeukwu, Ihendinihu & Nwachukwu, 2021). While large corporations are capable of paying the government's taxes, there are still complaints about the financial burden of taxes and their impact on financial performance. Budgetary and financial performance issues become prevalent, resulting in the early demise of SMEs (Tabet & Onyeukwu, 2019).

Multiple Taxation or Multiplicity of Taxes (MT) is a term that refers to unconstitutional and compulsory payments collected primarily by local and state governments without legal authority (Ilemona, Nwite & Oyedokun, 2019). It is a situation in which a taxpayer is compelled to pay the same or similar taxes by two (2) or more levels of government in a desperate attempt to increase their revenue base (Faloyin, 2015). Multiple taxation occurs when the same level of government imposes two or more taxes on the same base (Abiola, 2012). Multiple taxation also involves a situation in which an individual's or corporation's profit, or wealth is taxed more than once (Adum, 2018). Taxes are broadly classified into two types: direct and indirect taxes. Multiple taxation of a business or individual refers to a situation in which the same profit or income that is taxable in Nigeria has been taxed by another tax authority in Nigeria or another country outside Nigeria. In such cases, the taxpayer is typically granted relief for the prior tax paid or for which he may be liable. Specific arrangements are

made in order to avoid such multiple taxes or to provide appropriate relief in certain circumstances (Ocheni & Gemade, 2015).

Theoretical Review

Theory of Business Growth

Numerous authors have proposed theories regarding business growth. The earliest and most widely used theory is Gibrat's law of proportionate effect (LPE). A firm's growth rate is independent of its initial size. By extension, this implies that large firms are preferable in terms of private sector development, as they generate more jobs than small firms. In the learning model it was opined that younger firms acquire market knowledge over time, which helps them improve their performance. According to this model, young businesses grow at a faster rate than established businesses. The business growth theory opined that as a small firm commences and develops, it passes through some stages of growth, and each of these stages has its distinctive characteristics and challenges. He identified these stages of growth to include existence, survival, success, take-off, and resource maturity. Therefore, the over-taxing of a business trying to survive the difficult process of survival is not in the best interest of any state or national economy (Mbazulike, Ukairo, Umar, 2023) Furthermore, given that younger firms (businesses) are typically smaller than older firms (businesses), Jovanovich deduces that small firms grow faster than large firms. This is a process of convergence in which small firms eventually become as large as larger firms in the same sector (Ocheni & Gemade, 2015).

As a new small firm grows and develops, it passes through several growth stages such as existence, survival, success, take-off, and resource maturity. At each stage of development, a unique set of factors is critical to the survival and success of the business. The precise point in time at which a startup venture transforms into a new business has not been determined theoretically. The ideal business survival, on the other hand, could be equated to a firm that has completed the transaction to stage - two businesses at each of the five stages of small business development (Ocheni & Gemade, 2015).

Laffer Curve Theory of Taxation

The curve depicts a theoretical relationship between tax rates and the level of government revenue that results. With a particular emphasis on the elasticity of taxable income. The theory postulates that at extreme tax rates of 0% and 100%, the government collects zero (0) revenue due to changes in the behavior of taxpayers in response to the tax rate, either by losing their incentive to do business or by devising numerous ways to evade tax, similar to the 0% tax rate (Lawal & Aduku, 2016).

Additionally, the theory explained two of taxation's effects: the arithmetic and economic effects of tax rates on revenue. In the case of a decrease or an increase in tax rates, the two effects have the opposite effect on revenue. According to the arithmetic effect, lowering tax rates results in a reduction in tax revenue equal to the rate reduction. That is, tax revenue is a function of taxable income multiplied by the tax rate. When a tax rate is high and multiple impositions are imposed, negative economic effects such as tax evasion and disinvestment outweigh the arithmetic effect, resulting in a decline in tax revenue (Lawal & Aduku, 2016).

Empirical Review

Adewara, Dagunduro, Falana and Busayo (2023) assessed the effect of multiple taxation on the financial performance of small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in Ekiti State, Nigeria. The

performance and growth of business enterprises, especially small and medium enterprises (SMEs), have been hindered by a multiplicity of taxes causing the untimely liquidation of most businesses. In this regard, this study examined the effect of multiple taxations on the financial performance of SMEs in Ekiti State, Nigeria. The study used a survey research method and analyzed it with correlation coupled with multiple regression analysis. The population comprises all registered and functional SMEs located in Ado Ekiti, Nigeria, and have been in existence for over 5 years with valid proof of tax payment. The results found that multiple tax burdens and multiple tax administrations exhibited a significant negative relationship with the financial performance of SMEs in Ekiti State, Nigeria, while the ability to pay tax revealed a significant positive relationship. From the aforementioned results, it was concluded that multiple taxes served as a worm that deeply reduced the investment potential of SMEs and invariably affected the chunk of revenue generated by the sector in the state. It was therefore suggested that the Joint Tax Board in the state and other institutions responsible for multiple tax management should awaken to their functions and harmonize all government revenue to prevent the occurrence of multiple taxes from causing a burden and hindering the survival of SMEs in the state.

Mbazulike, Ukairo and Umar (2023) evaluated the effect of multiple taxation on the survival of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Katsina state, Nigeria. This is to find out if the multiple taxation has an impact on the survival of SMEs in Katsina state. To achieve this, the study adopted a survey design. Descriptive statistics was used to analyze the data and regression analysis was used to test the hypotheses. Results from the descriptive results showed that multiple taxation has a negative effect on the survival of SMEs in Katsina state. The regression analysis established that multiple taxation has no significant relationship with the survival of SMEs in Katsina state. The study therefore recommended that precedence be given to the size of SMEs in Katsina state as it relates to their profits when making tax laws so as to avoid multiple taxation.

Akpan, Ime and Ikoroha (2021) studied the effect of multiple taxations on smes growth in Akwa Ibom state. In order to carry out this study, specified research objectives were drawn from which null hypotheses were formulated and used for the study. The research design for this study is a survey design. The population of the study consisted of all SMEs operators in Uyo urban. Simple random sampling technique was used to select 398 respondents out of the population. The instrument used for data collection was questionnaire. Data from completed questionnaires was subjected to independent t-test analysis. The findings showed that effect of multiple taxations on the performance of SMEs in Uyo Urban. From all literatures reviewed, the researchers deduced that the development and operation of SMEs has economic impact on the nation. The study recommended that all SMEs should endeavor to pay their taxes as at when due. This should be done by the Government providing enabling environment for them to operate and see it as one of the benefits accrued to such payment of taxes to the Government. Also, Government should adequately create awareness on the need for SMEs to pay their taxes appropriately. Government should consider increasing tax incentives and exemptions as this will not only attract investors who are potential taxpayers, it will encourage voluntary compliance and ultimately leads to expansion of existing business interests of the SMEs in Akwa Ibom State as well as Nigeria as a whole. If these are done all SMEs will willingly pay their taxes as at when due.

Onyeukwu, Ihendinihu and Nwachukwu (2021) evaluated the effect of multiple taxation on financial performance of hospitality firms in Abia State, Nigeria. The aim is to map the extent to which multiple taxation impede the survival and success of hotel businesses in the state. Ex post facto research design was adopted and data for analysis collected from the demand notices, evidence of payment for all the classes of taxes payable in the state, financial records and statements of 21 hotels in Umuahia for a period of 9 years. The multiple linear regression technique was employed to analyze the data generated. Findings from the study reveal that multiple taxation (proxy by non-statutory fees and levies collectible by the state) has significant effect on both total revenue and profit before tax of the hospitality firms under study. This paper recommends that the state government and various local governments should concentrate on those taxes the law provided to enhance survival and excrescency of firms in the sector. Instead of duplicating and enacting more tax laws in the state, laws should be enacted to apprehend criminal elements that hide under the shadow of government to collect illegal taxes.

Ihenyen, Ayodeji and Benson (2021) examined the effect of multiple taxation on financial performance of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Bayelsa State. This cost primarily concerns multiple-taxation, enormous tax burdens, levies, and charges. This research examines the effect of multiple taxation on the investments in SMEs. The study used survey design with SME population of 100. Questionnaire was used to collect data. Simple percentages/frequencies were used to analyze the data and the research hypotheses were tested with ANOVA. It was found that multiple taxation has negative effect on SMEs investment. Furthermore, the relationship between SMEs investment and its ability to pay tax is significant. The researcher recommends that government should develop a tax policy that considers the enhancement of SMEs' capital allowance when imposing taxes. Government should provide uniform tax policies that will favors the development of business in Bayelsa state and should also put into consideration the size of business when formulating tax policies.

Oboh and Dabor (2020) carried out a study on the impact of multiple taxation on small and medium-scale enterprises (SMEs) in Nigeria using a library research approach. From the review of prior studies, it was revealed that multiple taxation has a negative impact on the performance, growth and survival of SMEs in Nigeria and multiple taxation occurs mostly in the local government compared to other levels of governments. This study concludes that multiple taxation is a great threat to the growth and survival of SMEs in Nigeria. This study therefore recommends Federal, State and Local governments to adhere strictly to the provisions of the law by collecting only those taxes within their jurisdictions. Also, there should be a review and a further amendment of the schedule to the Principal Act to harmonize the taxes and levies collected by each tier of government especially the State and Local governments. As a result, the state and local government should jointly collect a single market taxes and levies, road taxes and motor park levies. This will help to reduce the incidence of multiple taxation on SMEs in Nigeria.

Ilemona, Nwite and Oyedokun (2019) examined the effects of multiple taxation on the growth of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Nigeria. The aim is to investigate the extent to which multiple taxes affect the operation of SMEs in the country using expansionary rate of these businesses as surrogate for growth. Data for the study were obtained through responses from questionnaire designed on a five (5) point likert scale. Out of 193 questionnaires administered on staff and owners of SMEs on Lokoja – Kogi State, 131 of them were returned

representing approximately 68% response rate. The responses were empirically analyzed using non-parametric statistics comprising mean score, standard deviation, and z-test. The results suggest that multiple taxes have negatively affected the growth of SMEs in Nigeria as many operators of these businesses expressed their unwillingness to venture into new enterprises or expand the existing ones for fear of multiple taxes that continue to take a significant portion of their earnings. The study recommends that government at all levels in the country should address the issue of multiple taxes on SMEs by restricting to collecting only those taxes within their tax jurisdiction as stipulated by law. Further, provision should be made in Nigeria. Tax laws for stiff penalties against any tier of government, tax officials and tax agencies using orthodox, unfriendly, and illegal means to enforce multiple taxes on operators of SMEs in Nigeria.

Tabet and Onyeukwu (2019) examined the impact of multiple- taxation on small and medium scale enterprise finance performance, in Nigeria, particularly Abuja metropolis. This study surveyed fifteen (15) selected SMEs within the Abuja metropolis precisely AMAC area, with a population of four hundred and fifteen (415) respondents and a sample size of two hundred (200), as calculated using RAOSOFT Sample Size Calculator. A total of two hundred (200) questionnaires were administered. One hundred and seventy-eight (178) copies representing (89%) of the questionnaire were properly completed and retrieved while twenty-two (22) questionnaires representing (11%) were not retrieved. Primary source of data was used to gather information for the study and the main instrument of data collection was the questionnaire. The data were presented in tables as frequency distribution in the data analysis; the techniques of percentage frequencies were used. The hypotheses were tested using ANOVA (analysis of variance) at 5% significance level. Having analyzed the data, it was found that the majority of the respondents strongly agreed with all the questions posed with regards to the effects of multiple- taxation and disproportionate multiple- taxation on the finance performance of SMEs in Abuja. The study concluded that there is strong correlation between Multiple-taxation and the financial performance of SMEs in Abuja, Nigeria; there is also strong correlation between Disproportionate multiple taxation practices constitute a major challenge in the budgetary and planning performance of SMEs in Abuja, Nigeria. In view of these findings and conclusions, the researcher recommends, further studies on current taxation policies to ensure that they meet the criteria of good taxes according to Adam Smith in the wealth of nation. Training and awareness programs for tax agents, SMEs owners and their employees should be encouraged by the Nigerian Government. Comprehensive vetting of tax levies from government bodies and states by the federal government to weed out unnecessary multiple- taxation. Deregulation of disproportionate taxes to correlate with SMEs incomes. Consolidating all taxes as a lump paid directly to an assigned government account in correlation to income, after which the tax authorities can disseminate according to an agreed sharing ratio to various government purses instead of having multiple and closely related taxes at the same time.

Zayol, Duenya and Gberindye (2018) carried out a study to ascertain the effect of multiple taxation on financial performance of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Benue State. The population of the study was 816 and the sample size of 268 respondents was adopted using the Taro Yamane formula at a 5% error margin. The study adopted a survey design via questionnaire. Multiple regression was used for analysis in the study. The study found out that

duplication of Business Premises Registration Tax, Development Levy and Market Taxes have a significant negative effect on financial performance of SMEs and as a result affects their profitability negatively. The study, therefore, recommends that government should ensure that activities of touts in collecting illegal taxes from SMEs are stopped, also government should desist from collecting similar taxes under different names and collapse all taxes of such nature into one form of tax. Finally, government should ensure that only the amount stipulated by law is collected as tax and a clear jurisdiction of each tax should be expressly stated.

Methodology

This study adopted a survey research method that included a questionnaire, and a review of prior records and publications because this study is collecting respondents' views, perspectives, or opinions on a particular issue. This method was chosen because it is effective at eliciting opinions, attitudes, and descriptions, as well as establishing cause and effect relationships. The study population is comprised of 375 small and Medium-Sized Enterprises in Ibadan, Oyo State, from the population of SMEs in Oyo state which stood at 6,131. We calculated our sample size statistically using Yaro Yamani's formula. Questionnaires were distributed to the management staff of each of the sampled Small and Medium Scale Enterprises in Ibadan, Oyo State, resulting in a total distribution of 375 questionnaires. ANOVA will be used to analyze the hypotheses.

Results and Presentation of Data

Table 1: Demographic Data Analysis of Respondents

Variables	Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	152	40.5
	Female	223	59.5
	Total	375	100
Form of Business	Sole Proprietorship	123	32.8
	Private Limited Company	99	26.4
	Partnership	83	22.1
	Joint Venture	70	18.7
	Total	375	100
Position in Business	Owner	124	33.1
	Chief Accountant	66	17.6
	Manager	111	29.6
	Finance Manager	74	19.7
	Total	375	100
Highest Educational Qualification	Primary School Cert	27	7.2
	O'level Certificate	80	21.3
	First Degree	77	20.5
	Master's degree	104	27.7
	Higher Degree	87	23.2
	Total	375	100

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 1 shows the classification of respondents according to gender, form of business, [position in business and their highest educational qualification. It shows distinction between male and

female, 59.5% of the respondents are Females, while 40.5% of them were Males. This revealed that majority of the study respondents were females. The table also revealed the form of Business of the sampled respondents, 32.8% of the respondents were sole proprietorship, 26.4% were private limited company, 22.1% are partnership and 18.7% were joint venture. Thus, sole proprietorships were the highest respondents of the study. The table and figure 4.1.4 showed the position in business of respondents. The survey revealed that 33.1% of the respondents were the business owner, 29.6% respondents were managers, 19.7% of them were finance managers while 17.6% of them were Chief accountant. Hence, business owners were the highest respondents of the study. The table also showed the highest educational qualification of the respondents. From the information gathered 7.2% of the qualifications were primary school certificate holders, 21.3% were secondary school certificate holders, 20.5% were first degree holders, 27.7% of the respondents were holders of master’s degree while higher degree holders were 23.2%. Therefore, first degree holders were the major respondents of the study.

Hypotheses Testing

Hypothesis One

H0₁: There is no significant relationship between multiple taxation and SMEs’ Performance.

Table 2: Result of PPMC showing significant relationship between multiple taxation and SMEs’ Performance

Variable	Mean	Std. Dev.	N	R	P	Remark
Multiple Taxation	11.83	1.436	375	.128**	.005	Sig.
SMEs performance	12.62	1.285				

*Sig. at .05 level

Table 2 shows that there was a positive significant relationship between multiple taxation and SMEs performance ($r = .128^{**}$, $N = 375$, $p < .05$) in Oyo State. The result rejected the null hypothesis and accepted the alternate hypothesis which states there is a significant relationship between multiple taxation and SMEs performance in Oyo State.

Hypothesis Two

H0₂: The relationship between SMEs’ size and its ability to pay taxes does not significantly affect their Performance.

Table 3: Result of PPMC showing the relationship between SMEs’ size and its ability to pay taxes does not significantly affect their Performance.

Variable	Mean	Std. Dev.	N	R	P	Remark
SMEs’ Size and Ability to Pay Taxes	12.83	2.041				

			375	.216*	.000	Sig.
SMEs performance	12.62	1.285				

*Sig. at .05 level

Table 3 shows that there was a significant relationship between SMEs' size and its ability to pay taxes does not significantly affect their Performance ($r = .216^{**}$, $N = 375$, $p < .05$) of SMEs Holders in Oyo State. The result rejected the null hypothesis and accepted the alternate hypothesis which states there is a significant relationship between SMEs' size and its ability to pay taxes does not significantly affect their Performance.

Discussion of Findings

The results clearly showed that there is a significant relationship between multiple taxation and SMEs performance in Ibadan, Oyo State. This result is in line with the research work carried out in Benue state which revealed that that duplication of Business Premises Registration Tax, Development Levy and Market Taxes have a significant negative effect on financial performance of SMEs and as a result affects their profitability negatively (Zayol, Duenya & Abraham Gberindye, 2018). Also, the result is also in line with the study conducted in Abia state which revealed that multiple taxation (proxy by non-statutory fees and levies collectible by the state) has significant effect on both total revenue and profit before tax of the hospitality firms under study (Onyeukwu, Ihendinihu & Nwachukwu, 2021).

Conclusion and Recommendations

Multiple taxation has a significant negative effect on the financial performance of SMEs in Ibadan, Oyo state. To ensure that SMEs succeed, the tax system must encourage their survival. Thus, tax collection, assessment, and utilization must be geared toward SMEs survival and performance, as a consequence of this, the country's economic development will be influenced.

Consequently, the study recommends that.

1. The government repeal tax laws inimical to survival and growth of SMEs and unify all tax frameworks in order to dissuade tax duplication by state organs and its cronies.
2. Additionally, the activities of phony tax officials and touts who collect fees, levies, and taxes should be checked by the government. Nigeria's tax system must work collaboratively to protect and promote SMEs in order for them to make meaningful contributions to economic growth.
3. Furthermore, it is prudent to identify and deal with agents engaged in illegal, multiple tax collection against SMEs and mobile courts established to convict offenders with the unnecessary delays in dispensing justice as delay occasional warrant culprits buy out of judgment.

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